

Possibilities of new poetic image in Uzbek children's poetry

Ruzimatova Gulzoda Sharipovna

(Teacher of the Department of Primary Education Methodology of UrSU)

Children's literature is the beginning of literature, the birthplace of literature. Because the love for literature begins in this period, it is this period that gives motivation for figurative thinking, poetic imagination, prepares the ground for the formation of literary and artistic views. This, in turn, requires the creator to approach not just a set of thoughts infused with spiritual and educational views, but the most basic aspect that gives him the right to an artistic work, i.e. artistry, artistic skill. After all, "artisticness is not an addition or addition to a literary work, but a necessary condition of the work that it brings the work into the world of art, gives the right to call it a work of art. It is because of this artistry that the ideological power of the work is revealed." Works written for children also educate the reader's artistic-aesthetic taste, his world of emotions, instill the spark of the so-called spiritual ocean into the hearts, if they can meet the criteria of high artistry. If we understand the childish mind of children, if we take into account their young characteristics and individual nature, we will be sure that art is the most important aspect of children's literature. Belinsky writes about this: "Poetry speaks with images. Children do not require conclusions, proofs, logical consistency. They need images, colors, and sounds." For this, "a person who writes a book for children must be a master artist, an experienced pedagogue, and a master of language."

We must emphasize that children's literature, like our general literature, is in constant search and movement. A child is always a child. He does not choose time and place, nation. The phrase "Bola-da akhir", which is often used among our people, is

sometimes used in a state where children are alien to the world, their hearts and minds are unable to comprehend concepts that cannot be digested, and sometimes we adults learn a lot from them. is used to indicate necessity. After all, Andersen's hero did not decide in vain: "Adults are very, very strange people"! They have their own world, their own thinking, their own spirituality, of course, their own literature.

Rustam Nazar writes about himself: "I tried to make children's poetry serious, to introduce elements of adult literature into it." In fact, the lyrical heroes of the poems he created are intelligent, independent-minded children who carefully observe a certain reality and events and make serious opinions:

What is black, what is white.

I understand quickly.

Look at the world,

I will discover your secrets,

says the hero of the poem "The World and Me". This lyrical hero understands and feels the various secrets of the colorful world with his mind and consciousness, and expresses his unique opinions, which will fill both young readers and adults alike with thoughts.

In "Color Fountain", the poet sees the true image of people who don't wear makeup, whose faces are shiny, and whose insides are shaky. The fountain, which was showing off like a rainbow in the rain of turf lights, returns to its original state when the lights are turned off. Observing this situation, the lyrical hero expresses his attitude as follows:

There's no point in cheating.

Did he realize his mistake?

It is necessary to look around

The colors you have!..

"Looking at the world, I will discover your secrets," the lyrical hero in "Color Fountain" separates black and white. Seeing the film about Dersu Uzala, who calls both a tree and an animal a man, he is surprised by this:

Why some people
They look for evil -
Calling each other crazy
They say it's a rat?!

Comparing the hero of the film, who treats every creature as a human ("he talks like a man, even to a tiger"), and people who call each other "rats" and "rats" while being human in life, the lyrical hero is deep in thought. At the core of his question is the desire to avoid vices such as evil and wickedness, to show love and honor to each other.

An old man puts a flower next to the eternal fire, telling a "silly story" from "Years of a distant war", "pain enters his body". In this case, the cause of this pain is known - it is the torture of distant memories. At that moment, a "strange teenager" also "rushed up". Follow him without haste:

He did not look at the monument,
There is no meaning in his eyes.
... It's a cold day
Warming up a bit!

- says the lyrical hero and expresses his attitude in a cutting tone while drawing the cold (actually cold, emotionless) image of the critical teenager ("There is no meaning in his gaze"). The image of the old man and the teenager in the poem is embodied not only as two generations, but also as people of two different worlds: the selfless (old man) who fought for goodness and peace, and the selfish (teenager) who only cares about his own peace and pleasure.

Such selfish people will never think of bringing any benefit to the country even after they grow up one day. The lyrical hero of the poem "Chiganoq" is extremely happy with such things. "If you listen to the shell, it's like the roar of the sea." It's as if this tiny creature said, "The sea is the original source, let the earth be blessed with its never-tiring, never-tiring song." The lyrical hero feels a great meaning from this small shell: he is loyal to his country, like a patriot who lives with the memory of the Motherland even in separation. The lyrical hero continues to think:

What about people? Some
Unproven and cunning.
In his words, for the country,
He is ready to die.
But if you listen
To their hearts,
listen to
A very strange sound, —

in such lines, his language is different, while his language describes the appearance of other people, he regrets and regrets that they are actually smaller than a shell:

Housing, livelihood
Fading tongues -
Rumblings inside
The market is bustling.

When the sound of the sea is heard from the shell, the "buzz of the market" "buzzes" inside some. These two words - the sound of the great sea and the roar of the bazaar describe the spiritual state of people with two different inner worlds. The

secret of the "marketable" people whose inner world is alienated and only worried about living is revealed. This is a sad picture of some people who can't even be a shell. In general, in Rustam Nazar's poems, the dream of seeing life more perfect and beautiful, a person perfect and glorious shines. For this, a person must strive tirelessly, rise, and reach the value of time and life! It is impossible to crawl like a turtle. Even if the destination of the turtle is far away, there is no need to hurry, because it lives for 400 years. "But what about you, boy, why are you lying around, busy with all your work, lost in idle thoughts?" he scolds and laughs. The call and demand of the lyrical hero of the poem "Tortoise" is strict:

Appreciate every opportunity,
Create a chaman, build a castle.
Every living thing that moves
He will not live for four centuries!

The preciousness of every moment is emphasized figuratively and impressively even by the language of the lyrical hero of the poem "Measurable Time". Describing the pain of Sabir, who did not win the race because he was only one minute late, he emphasizes that it is not just a competition, but every moment in life should be appreciated:

Open your eyes, my dear.
Time is measured, if enough —
Just a minute
Fulfill your destiny!

The grandkids invite the grandkids to take a rest and stretch out their legs for the father who is an example of spending his time and life on good and good deeds.

Then:

My grandmother laughs: "A living soul -

Need to work hard.

He is old and the ground

To hide it."

A lot has been said in fiction about the fact that a person leaves a good name behind himself in this life. The recitation of the ageless noble creed from the old man's tongue gives it a special spirit. In this poem, the meaning is more impressive based on the contrast between "aging" and "rejuvenating". If this meaning and advice were to be expressed in the dry form of "It is necessary to work, it is necessary to make the earth green, it is necessary to make it bloom", it would make the neck of a young reader stiffen. In the poem "Lazy", those who are given to indifference are harshly criticized, as if it is possible to burn the snow. The poet "pinch-pinches" the lazy like this: The soulless lazy,

The search is complete, // Extinguishes the melting // Burning fire!

Rustam Nazar's poems mostly have a clear plot. The skill of the poet is that he describes a certain reality, situation and landscape in bright and colorful colors, based on which he puts forward a certain thought and idea. The important thing is that he can tell something completely new, an interesting idea even about things that are known to everyone. He artistically elaborates and convinces his opinion. For example, autumn paints everything yellow "in spite of the trees". Only the spruce is always blue. The poet explains it like this: Do not dare to paint, // Be afraid of needles!

A wonderful poetic find! A new interpretation and artistic proof of a well-known thing that no one has thought of: autumn does not dare to turn yellow because it is afraid of its needles. Or take the poem "Disciplined Tram". First of all, how can the tram be "disciplined"? And the poet justifies it artistically:

He always walks the same way, // He doesn't lose track. // Like a bus, // He doesn't stick his nose into every street.

A simple, fluent and figurative image soothes the reader and makes him believe in the words of the poet. Based on the characteristic sign, shape or other aspect of things-phenomena, the figurative meaning of them means that these artistic findings convince the reader without words. Based on these artistic foundations, a specific poetic content is formed, and a concise and impressive conclusion is presented at the end of the poem. This unexpectedness and urgency suddenly gives the reader a pleasant jolt. It quickly and easily conveys the poet's poetic purpose to the reader. The poet's poems serve to improve the level of thought, worldview, growth and deepening of reasoning ability of young readers. He encourages them to look at life with a sharp eye and a sharp mind, to appreciate goodness. It elevates and enlarges their hearts and spiritual levels. Because, as the poet himself admitted:

I took my lessons for you,

Let it go to your heart.

Children are grown up,

Let the adults have children!

References:

1. "Children's literature" (Teacher publishing house, Tashkent, 2013)
2. Belinsky. V. G. Selected works. Volume II. Page 28.
3. Karimov N. Hamid Olimjon's poetic skills. -Tashkent, 1964. pp. 44-45.
4. Qahhor A. Conversation with young people. -Tashkent, 1968. Page 55.